

EEG-BASED METHODS FOR DIAGNOSING COLOR VISION DEFICIENCY: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW

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Abstract

Color vision deficiency (CVD) is one of the most common disorders related to visual impairment. Individuals with this condition are unable to differentiate between different colors due to a lack or impairment of one or more-color photoreceptors in their retinas. This disorder can be diagnosed by multiple approaches. This review paper seeks to offer a thorough summary of the studies done in the area of applying BCI technology for the diagnosis of CVD. The main purpose of this review paper is to help researchers to know how using BCI to diagnose CVD could be improved and used in the future.

Index Terms: Brain Computer Interface (BCI), Classification, Color Vision Deficiency (CVD), EEG Processing, Event Related Potential (ERP), Feature Extraction, Ishihara Test, Steady State Visually Evoked Potential (SSVEP).

1. INTRODUCTION

Color vision deficiency (CVD) is considered to be one of the most common vision disorders. It is the inability to differentiate between different colors and shades under typical lighting conditions [1]. Globally, CVD affects approximately 1 in 200 women and 1 in 12 men [2], indicating a higher prevalence in males. This occurs as children can inherit CVD through the X chromosome. Men possess one X chromosome, while females possess two. In females, both X chromosomes (inherited from the mother and father) should carry the CVD genes, but this rarely happens. Conversely, males only have one X chromosome inherited from their mother, making it more common for them to have the CVD gene [3]. Also, the prevalence rates vary among populations. According to reports, the prevalence rates are 3.28% in Saudi Arabia, 8.4% in European populations, 7.3% in Turkey, 8.7% in India and Jordan, and 4% to 6.5% in Chinese people [4], [5], [6], [7]. These variations are caused by genetic factors, as studies have shown that gene frequencies differ from one population to another [7]. Other reasons for these variations include environmental factors, such as medication reactions and exposure to chemicals [8]. Moreover, consanguineous marriages, which are more common in Muslim populations, may increase the prevalence of genetic disorders, including CVD [9].

Although CVD impacts individuals across various ethnic and geographic demographics, a notable proportion of instances remain undetected or unacknowledged during the initial phases of life [1]. Such occurrences may arise due to a dearth in appropriate and precise diagnostic techniques targeting this disorder. People with CVD usually experience unfavorable effects in their daily lives, as some research has shown that these individuals

may also lack awareness [10], including students whose academic performance has been negatively affected by CVD [1]. However, early diagnosis of CVD can help individuals manage the condition and plan their future career paths.

Early detection of CVD is crucial as it allows for timely intervention and support for affected individuals, particularly in educational and occupational settings. When CVD is detected earlier, it enables individuals to accommodate and intervene to address potential academic challenges and optimize their learning experience. Certain occupational environments consider color discrimination to be vital and significant, such as aviation, electrical engineering, and graphic design. Therefore, early detection of CVD ensures individuals can make informed career choices and avoid limitations [2]. Another crucial point is that if CVD is recognized early, other vision diseases that may be linked to it, like amblyopia and refractive errors, may be identified earlier as well [6]. Overall, early detection of CVD improves the wellbeing and quality of life of those affected.

At the moment, none of the available tests can fully evaluate color vision accurately [11]. The most commonly used methods to assess color vision currently include the widely used Ishihara test, the Farnsworth-Munsell (FM) 100 Test, and the Anomaloscope [11]. Although these methods can assess color vision, they have some limitations that may affect their efficiency. One such limitation is that these tests require a behavioral response, which makes it impossible for individuals with locked-in syndrome, for example, to use these tests due to their physical and communication limitations. The fact that these tests are subjective and cannot accurately gauge how the user sees variations in hue is another problem. Furthermore, users must complete considerable training prior to the exam, which is not doable for many people with neurological impairments. Finally, because some users can memorize the solutions, the outcomes of these examinations may be manipulated.

All these limitations highlight the importance of finding alternative approaches that can be used to diagnose CVD efficiently. In recent years, the utilization of Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCIs) has proven to be effective in various medical applications. A brain computer interface (BCI) is a technology that permits brain-to-external device connection. It translates brain signals, such as electroencephalography (EEG), into instructions for controlling an external device. Since BCI provides an alternative method of communication to interact with the external world, they are mainly targeted to those who are unable to use conventional control and communication methods; due to various disorders, such as spinal cord injury and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis [12]. As it can offer reliable information about the underlying brain processes, BCI technology can also be employed for diagnostic purposes. The diagnostic of CVD is one instance of a BCI system that could be used for diagnostic purposes. This review seeks to offer a thorough summary of the studies done in the area of applying BCI technology for the diagnosis of CVD.

2. NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL BASIS OF COLOR VISION

As Newton said, "the rays are not colored" [13]. This leads to the fact that the perception of colors occurs due to the complex neurons that undergo computations. The human eye's retina comprises specialized cells referred to as cone photoreceptors. These cells are responsible for color vision. The cone photoreceptors have the task of perceiving distinct colors through the detection of light wavelengths. A diverse assortment of tints is present, leading to a multitude of cones. The initial type of cone, known as S-cone, has an enhanced sensitivity to short wavelengths, allowing it to perceive the color blue. The second type, called M-cone, demonstrates a noticeable sensitivity to intermediate wavelengths, indicating the color green. Lastly, the last type, referred to as L-cone, exhibits an acute sensitivity to long wavelengths, thus representing the color red. The mechanism of color vision begins when the cones absorb the light that enters the eye. The brain processes the signals that the optic nerve transmits after that. The brain subsequently decodes these information, which enables us to see various hues [14].

Individuals with CVD struggle to perceive red, green, and blue hues because of the lack or abnormalities of the cone cells in the eye [10]. Consequently, this results in the retina's incapacity to adequately react to various light wavelengths [2], which means failure to properly transmit the signals to the brain, leading to an incorrect reception of the visual information. The causes of CVD can be genetic or acquired. Genetic etiologies are linked to the transmission of the X-linked chromosome, in contrast, acquired etiologies are correlated with chronic illnesses such as diabetes and sickle cell anemia [15]. In addition, there are different types of CVD, and each type depends on the affected cone cell in the eye as illustrated in Fig. 1. If one cone is abnormal, anomalous trichromacy occurs. Protanomaly is characterized by the presence of an aberrant cone responsible for perceiving red. Deuteranomaly, on the other hand, is marked by an abnormality in the cone responsible for perceiving green. Lastly, tritanomaly is observed when the cone responsible for perceiving blue is abnormal. Moreover, if a person lacks one cone, meaning they have only two cones, dichromacy occurs, resulting in a total absence of a specific color. However, there exist three classifications of dichromacy, specifically protanopia, deuteranopia, and tritanopia [10].

Table 1: Color Vision Deficiency Types

	CVD Type	Cause
Anomalous trichromacy	Protanomaly	Abnormal L-cone
	Deuteranomaly	Abnormal M-cone
	Tritanomaly	Abnormal S-cone
Dichromacy	Protanopia	Missing L- cone
	Deuteranopia	Missing M-cone
	Tritanopia	Missing S-cone

3. EEG AS A DIAGNOSTIC TOOL

The EEG, which is considered an electrophysiological technique for recording the brain's electrical activity, was pioneered in 1924. The primary source of the EEG is believed to be the cortical pyramidal neurons in the cerebral cortex that are aligned with the brain's

surface. It is thought that the neural activity observed through the EEG is a result of the combined impact of both excitatory and inhibitory postsynaptic potentials generated by groups of neurons firing in a synchronized manner [16].

It was proved that the EEG is considered to be a significant diagnostic method for non-invasive studies on neurological disorders. It is an efficient method for identification of neurological disorder biomarkers, which leads to valuable insights into the disorder. The slowing of EEG rhythms, for example, can indicate an abnormality of the brain function, indicating abnormal condition of the human. To use the EEG as a diagnostic tool, it is crucial to analyze the signals and relate the changes with the specific condition. Nevertheless, there are some limitations related to using EEG as a diagnostic tool. Such limitation is that EEG measures the activity of the brain on the scalp and not directly from the brain affecting the spatial resolution. This makes it challenging to identify a specific brain region involved in a specific disorder. Also, EEG data involves a complex analysis which makes it important to be analyzed by an expert. Other limitations encompass the factors affecting the EEG recording, such as eye movements and muscle activity that contribute in introducing noise in the signal affecting the accuracy [17], [18], [19].

Since the CVD contributes to altering the EEG signals, the changes could be used to detect the biomarkers to diagnose the CVD. The studies showed that the EEG is highly affected by the color perception, which indicates that it could be used to detect CVD. The nature of vision is heterogeneous which makes manual detection difficult; however, machine learning application related to CVD could be applied in order to eliminate human errors [20].

4. EEG-BASED APPROACHES FOR DIAGNOSING CVD

Generally, the selection of the EEG-based BCI's design depends on the chosen paradigm, and at the moment, popular approaches in the field include Motor Imagery (MI), Event-Related Potential (ERP), and Steady State Visually Evoked Potential (SSVEP). In the field of CVD, the SSVEP has been utilized in several studies. The SSVEP is considered as a constant, regular response to a repeated visual stimulus [21]. This technology enables users to select from multiple commands by focusing on visual stimuli; thus, the SSVEP represents a steady response that occurs when individuals are exposed to repetitive visual stimuli [21]. Other reasons that make SSVEP a good choice in such studies include its high signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and the low artifacts [22]. Even though there are many studies have been discussed using SSVEP in the BCI field, most of them have discussed the techniques in signal processing that could improve BCI performance and not consider the fact that some parameters, such as shape and color, have significant effects on SSVEP [23]. This highlights the importance of considering the properties of the stimulus in the upcoming studies in this field. Approximately before 2020, there had been no significant advancements in using SSVEP to diagnose CVD. It is a new development that deserves researchers' attention to improve the healthcare field.

5. ERP APPROACHES FOR DIAGNOSING CVD

Despite the fact that SSVEP has been considered by different studies as a good choice in diagnosing CVD, other approaches, such as ERP, have been used in this field. Bieber et al. [24] used silent substitution to measure visually evoked potentials (VEPs) in infants to detect CVD. The ERP that includes VEPs is defined as a transient response to specific stimuli [25]. The silent substitution is a technique that stimulates a specific cone cell in the retina by using metamers, which are pairs of lights, while minimizing the response from other types of cones. It depends on adjusting the intensities of different wavelengths of light to stimulate the desired cone type [26]. They analyzed the effects of the stimuli on the EEG signal by a vector voltmeter where the results showed response differences between healthy and color-deficient infants.

Also, Thomas and Umamaheswari [27], as well as other studies [28], [29] have investigated the relationship between color perception and brain activity by analyzing EEG signals while using color stimuli. In [27], the subjects were asked to identify the matching colors of the test color from a set of shades of the basic colors (red, green, blue) while their EEG signals were being recorded. They then calculated the energy of each EEG signal. For [28], the subjects were shown a few colors of the VIBGYOR spectrum, with a neutral grey background separating each color, and their EEG signals were recorded from several locations in the brain. The researchers then analyzed the spectral width of each EEG signal. Meanwhile, in [29], the subjects were shown a stimulus set consisting of different shapes with different colors (red, green, blue) on the computer screen, and their EEG was recorded. Then, the conventional band power values were obtained. All the studies have proven that there is a difference in EEG responses to different colors. However, none of the three studies has performed the experiment on a subject suffering from CVD.

Another study [30] estimated the power spectral density (PSD) of EEG signals recorded while presenting stimuli of different colors to the subjects, including red, green, yellow, and blue. The study found that the PSD differed for each color, with the classification rate being highest for red and lowest for yellow. This finding could have a significant impact on diagnosing CVD using ERP. Moreover, Thomas et al. [31] have developed a portable embedded device using Python and Beagle board to analyze the effects of CVD on EEG signals. Like the previously mentioned studies, they used color stimuli with the three basic colors (red, green, blue) while recording the EEG. They then calculated the deviation in the energy, where they observed more deviation in the particular color associated with CVD in the person. Also, Wicaksono et al. [32] have used ERP extracted from EEG signals acquired during Ishihara visual stimulus instead of color stimulus. They analyzed the signals using various methods, including Global Field Power (GFP), ERP Component Analysis, and Brain Topography Analysis. They found that the amplitude of the wave associated with the number that the individual cannot detect did not appear clearly, as if no visual process had occurred. Similarly, Ekhlesi et al. [33] used 38 plates of the Ishihara test to evaluate the EEG and determine which Ishihara plates yielded the best results in detecting CVD. They analyzed the signals using False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction and classified them using the K-nearest neighbour (KNN) classifier. They found that the

best electrodes showing differences between color-deficient and healthy individuals were observed in P4, T6, and O2 in certain frequency bands. Only men participated in this study; therefore, the results might not be representative for both genders.

6. SSVEP APPROACHES FOR DIAGNOSING CVD

In the field of using SSVEP to diagnose CVD, as mentioned earlier, there were no published studies regarding this before 2020, although it has been known for many years that SSVEP is affected by different colors. Xavier et al. [34] have studied the effects of some colors, which are red, green, blue, white, and gray, on SSVEP at three different frequencies (5, 12, 30) Hz. They investigated the frequency amplitudes using canonical correlation analysis (CCA). They concluded that each color generates a different amplitude and phase. The white and red colors produce the largest amplitude. They also found that the best SNR is achieved by using mid-range frequencies, such as 12 Hz. Another study [35] also concludes that the red color has the most accurate discrimination among other colors; this finding could be very useful in diagnosis of color vision deficiency (CVD). However, the studies stated that using white color is better than using red color to avoid the risk associated with red color, such as inducing epileptic seizures [34]. Also, it was concluded in [23] that colors with high wavelength, such as red, generate higher SSVEP amplitudes compared to colors with lower wavelengths, such as blue. Generally, many researchers studied color effects on SSVEP, but have rarely used this finding to diagnose CVD.

Zheng et al. [36] have used a method that depends on sweep SSVEP to diagnose CVD. They used a stimulus paradigm consisting of a red-green reversal checkboard with different luminance ratios to elicit the SSVEP. Then, they analyzed the signals using CCA and established a method to determine the type and severity of CVD by using an equiluminance turning curve. They considered the equiluminance point to occur when the two colors appear to have the same luminance. Moreover, Norton et al. [37] studied CVD detection using SSVEP based on a new method of metamers identification they called "metald." This method involves adjusting two light sources that have the same color appearance but differ in spectral distributions to be the same. They hypothesized that the metamer is identified by minimizing the SSVEP caused by two flickering light sources and found that people with normal color vision have an SSVEP that is close to zero, while people with CVD do not. As they mentioned, EEG measurements are often noisy, and the excessive use of filters can potentially impact the data, leading to decreased accuracy. Thus, Habibzadeh et al. [38] have tried to improve what was done in [37] by using Gaussian process regression to reduce the noise of the measurements, and they were able to enhance the performance of the method.

In SSVEP approaches, the stimulation frequency was different in each study. For example, in [34], the stimulation frequencies were 5, 12, 30 Hz, and in [36], the stimulation frequency was 15 Hz, while in [37], the stimulation frequency was 10 Hz. However, the effects of the stimulation frequency was investigated by E. Atkins et al. [39]. They considered the frequency range of (2-38) Hz and observed that hue stimulation led to eliciting larger SSVEP at lower frequencies, while illuminance stimulation led to eliciting

smaller SSVEP at lower frequencies. They also found that the best frequency for CVD assessment is 16 Hz. Their results indicate that CVD assessment based on SSVEP could be improved by optimizing the stimulation frequency.

Table 2: Summary of Existing Studies Utilizing EEG Signals for Diagnosing CVD

Reference	Year	Method/ Analysis	Channels	Extracted features	Findings
[24]	-	Silent substitution, vector voltmeter	Oz, O1, O2	Amplitude	Differences in EEG were observed between color deficient and healthy infants.
[27]	2016	Color stimulus, principal component analysis (PCA).	Cz, O1, Oz, O2 (10-20 international system)	Energy	Higher EEG energy for correct color choices compared with the incorrect choices.
[28]	2021	Colors stimulus, multifractal detrended fluctuation analysis (MFDFA) and multifractal detrended cross-correlation analysis (MFDXA).	F3, F4, F7, F8, Fz, P3, P4, O1, O2	Spectral width	The complexity of the EEG varies across different perceived colors
[29]	2021	Colors stimulus, Fourier transform, Quadratic Discriminant analysis, SVM, and KNN classifiers.	63 different channels	Conventional band power, Inverse solution of EEG waves	Different electrodes showed a significant impact of different colors.
[30]	2016	Color stimulus, Interval-Type II fuzzy classifier	F3, F4, Fz, P3, Pz, P4, O1, O2, T7, T8	PSD	Different PSD for each color with the highest classification rate observed for red and the lowest for yellow.
[31]	2017	Color stimulus, Python, Beagle board	Cz, O1, Oz, O2	Energy, entropy	There is more deviation in the energy of color-deficient people compared to healthy people.
[32]	2020	Ishihara plates stimulus, GPF, Brain Topography, and ERP Analysis	Fp1, Fp2, F3, Fz, F4, C3, Cz, C4, P7, P3, Pz, P4, P8, O1, Oz, O2 (10-20 international system)	Amplitude, latency	Variations in latency and amplitudes between healthy and color-deficient people.

[33]	2021	Ishihara plates stimulus, FDR correction, KNN Classifier	Fp1, Fp2, F3, F4, C3, C4, P3, P4, O1, O2, F7, F8, T3, T4, T5, T6, Fz, Cz, Pz (10-20 international system)	Frequency	People with CVD have different values for the frequency bands compared to individuals with normal color vision and the best results that showed differences were observed for the electrodes P4, T6, and O2.
[36]	2020	Sweep SSVEP, CCA, color vision severity index (ICVD)	PO3, PO4, POz, O1, O2 and Oz (10-20 international system)	Amplitude, frequency	The type and severity of CVD can be determined by ICVD
[37]	2021	SSVEP, Metamer Identification Algorithm (metalD), CCA	F3, Fz, F4, T7, C3, Cz, C4, T8, CP3, CP4, P3, Pz, P4, PO7, PO8, Oz (10-10 international system)	Frequency	People with normal color vision have an SSVEP that is close to zero, while people with CVD do not.
[38]	2022	SSVEP, Gaussian Process Regression (metalD+)	O1, Oz, O2, PO7, PO3, POz, PO4, PO8, P5, P3, P1, Pz, P2, P4, P6, CPz	Frequency	This method can improve the measurement and reduce noise compared to metalD method
[39]	2023	SSVEP, CCA	O1, Oz, O2, PO7, PO3, POz, PO4, PO8, P5, P3, P1, Pz, P2, P4, P6, CPz	Amplitude	CVD assessment efficiency depends on the visual stimulation frequency

7. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Studies have revealed that the features of EEG undergo changes based on different colors, such as alterations in frequency band values or signal complexity, these changes can serve as significant biomarkers for detecting CVD. The main steps utilized to classify EEG signals for CVD diagnosis comprise data collection, data pre-processing, feature extraction, feature selection, and classification [20].

Figure 1: Methodology for Detecting Color Vision Deficiency using EEG Signals

The first step, data collection, involves recording the EEG data of multiple subjects under different circumstances. The second step, data pre-processing, involves isolating the noise that usually accompanies EEG data, such as eye movements. The third step, feature extraction, involves extracting specific features, such as frequency domain, from the EEG signal. The fourth step, feature selection, involves selecting relevant features to minimize dimensionality. The final step, classification, involves training on the chosen features to classify the EEG signals into normal and CVD classes. Although the details of the steps may vary and not always united in the published studies, the typical approach includes spatial and spectral filtering of the data. Besides using filters such as the band-pass filter (BPF), low-pass filter (LPF), and high-pass filter (HPF) to eliminate environmental noises, and the notch filter to eliminate power line interference, other techniques have been employed to remove artifacts, such as eye blinking. These techniques include Signal Space Projection (SSP), which is used in [32], and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), which is used in [27], and [32]. The filtering parameters vary in every study as illustrated in Table 3. Note that the filtering parameters all depend on the procedures used in the study.

Table 3: Filters Parameters in Existed Studies

Reference	Filter	Fc
[27]	BPF	0.3-40 Hz
[32]	BPF	0.5-20 Hz
[36]	Online BPF	2-100 Hz
	Offline notch filter	48-52 Hz
[33]	LPF	40 Hz
	HPF	1.5 Hz
[37]	BPF: 4 th order	3-45 Hz
	Notch filter	60 Hz
[38]	BPF: 12 th order	5-55 Hz
[39]	BPF: 12 th order	4-85 Hz

There are various analysis techniques in the field of diagnosing CVD using EEG signals. These techniques include CCA and PCA, which have been widely utilized in previous researches. The CCA technique has been extensively employed in the examination of SSVEP in previous studies [36], [37], [38],[39]. It is commonly used to describe the

correlations among SSVEP signals from multiple channels and to measure the size of SSVEP in each trial, enabling the extraction of its features. While CCA is used to identify correlated patterns between two sets, PCA focuses on capturing the overall variance within a single set [27],[32]. When dimensionality reduction is required, PCA is typically preferred over CCA. However, both techniques can be employed for feature extraction. Moreover, in order to differentiate between healthy and color-deficient people, frequency features are usually used. After recording the EEG signal, frequency analysis, such as Fourier Transform or Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) are applied to identify the presence of frequency components corresponding to the stimuli [27].

Using machine learning algorithms makes it possible to automatically extract meaningful patterns and features from EEG signals, aiding in the classification process as they can handle the complex nature of EEG data. For example, the SVM algorithm has been used in [29] as it aims to find a hyperplane that separates data points of different classes with the largest margin. It is capable of capturing complex relationships and making accurate predictions. Another classifier, such as the KNN classifier, has been employed in some studies [29], [33] as it is simple, does not require explicit model training, and can handle both numerical and categorical features. Overall, most studies, such as [27], [30], [37], have used MATLAB for analysis and classification reasons.

8. CLINICAL APPLICATIONS AND CHALLENGES

Although some papers have studied CVD detection using EEG signals, there has not been much improvement in this area. There are so many challenges and areas for improvement that need to be considered in future work in this field. Firstly, there is the data challenge. A significant amount of data is required for training to be able to construct a good model. The unavailability of public dataset makes it important to have a large number of subjects in studies to construct a new dataset and obtain reliable results. Also, there is the emotions challenge, as the EEG signals can be affected by emotions. Therefore, it is important to consider the individuals' emotional states when gathering data. Moreover, there is the demographic challenge. Demographic factors such as age, gender, and race may affect the EEG signals, so, it is important to incorporate these factors in the analysis, which will require a lot of time and effort. Another thing is the ethical challenge, which includes obtaining permission from specific authorities and ensuring the desire of the subjects involved in the study. Finally, there is the standardization challenge. There are many factors that could affect EEG signal acquisition and analysis, such as electrode placement, signal processing techniques, and analysis methodologies. All of these factors make it difficult to standardize the procedures across different studies and research groups, while it is crucial for ensuring consistency and comparability of results [20]. Despite these challenges, using EEG signals to detect CVD can overcome many limitations of conventional diagnostic approaches. The behavioral response, which is considered a limitation as it relies on communication and excludes individuals with communication disabilities, can be overcome with the new method that relies on the brain's response, eliminating the need for direct communication with the individual. Additionally, the subjective characteristics associated with conventional methods, which

can be influenced by individual factors, can be overcome with the new objective method. The objective nature of the new method ensures that it remains unaffected by the individual's situation as it is based on observable data. Another advantage is that the new method does not require training, especially when compared to the anomaloscope, making it easier to use. Finally, while the conventional method can be easily manipulated, it is impossible to control one's brain signals. This inability to manipulate brain signals enhances the accuracy and reliability of CVD diagnostic methods. Overall, the advantages and problems that can be eliminated by the new method outweigh the disadvantages or challenges that may be encountered.

9. FUTURE DIRECTIONS AND RESEARCH PERSPECTIVES

In addition to the challenges mentioned earlier, the field of using EEG signals to diagnose CVD is relatively new and lacks established procedures. This highlights the importance and necessity of further research and improvements. Certain issues were not covered in earlier studies in this field, thus future studies must address these issues. According to [40] and [41], EEG data is highly affected by factors such as emotions and age; thus, it is important to consider this while recording EEG data in upcoming studies. Another factor that may affect the EEG data, which has not been mentioned in the reviewed studies, is the screen brightness during data recording. Additional areas that can be improved include enhancing feature extraction, feature selection, and classification accuracy processes as well as data processing procedures and methodologies.

10. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the available color vision assessments exhibit significant limitations, necessitating the exploration of alternative methods. Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of EEG signals in diagnosing CVD by observing its response to different colors. This finding holds significant implications for utilizing EEG signals and employing machine learning algorithms to classify and diagnose CVD non-invasively. The non-invasive use of EEG in the diagnosis of CVD opens up new options for study and clinical implementation. By leveraging the distinctive changes in SSVEP responses to different colors, for example, EEG-based approaches offer promising prospects in accurately identifying and classifying color vision deficiencies. Nonetheless, it is crucial to remember that there are some difficulties in this sector that will need to be solved in upcoming research. These challenges encompass refining the methodologies and protocols for capturing and analyzing EEG signals, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of diagnostic algorithms, and overcoming the limitations associated with user interfaces and usability. More research is also needed to create standard operating protocols, confirm the reliability of EEG-based CVD diagnosis in various populations, and investigate possible clinical applications.

Future research efforts should concentrate on overcoming the identified problems and knowledge gaps in light of these findings and their implications. The development of EEG-based CVD diagnosis depends critically on cooperation between researchers, physicians, biomedical engineers, and technology creators. By doing this, we may work to increase

diagnostic precision, broaden access to valid evaluations, and eventually raise the standard of care for people who have color vision problems.

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